

Factor that effect on consumer behavior: The case of boarding students

Waheed Akhtar¹, Mudassir Husnain²,

¹ MS Scholar, Faculty of Management Sciences, International Islamic University Islamabad

Waheedakhtar@gmail.com

² Faculty of Management Sciences, International Islamic University Islamabad,

mudassirhusnain@yahoo.com

Abstract

The objective of this paper is to investigate the buying behavior of boarding students in Pakistan. This is basically an empirical study and a scale was developed to find out the impact of nine variables namely Basic needs, Former experience, friend and family, Recommended by celebrities, product design, Product quality, Product price, Brand and Discount on price. The questionnaire was distributed among the respondents on the basis of convenience sampling. The results showed that the buying behavior of boarding students are affected all of these factors which are proposed by literature and theoretical framework. Findings from this study provide a useful framework for marketers to link their services; Basic needs, Former experience, friend and family, Recommended by celebrities, product design, Product quality, Product price, Brand and Discount on price thus enhancing their productivity and profitability in the Pakistani Telenor sector. In order to increase the external validity of results future research can be done using longitudinal designs.

Keywords: Basic Needs; Former Experience; Friends & Family; Recommended by Relatives; Consumer/Students Behavior; Products Design; Product Quality; Product price; Price Discount; Brand name.

1. Introduction

The past five decades, especially the last few years, have been exciting times in the field of consumer behavior. Many researchers are very interested to investigate the consumer behavior related to purchase decision. First of all economist study the consumer behavior early 300 years ago, led by John von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern, Nicholas Bernoulli started to examine the basis of consumer decision making (Richarme 2007). Consumer are concerned with their own interest and they are the rational decision maker (Schiffman AND Kanuk 2007, Zinkhan 1992). Howard developed the first consumer decision-model in 1963 (Du Plessis, Rousseau et al. 1991). Consumer behavior defined "consumer behavior is the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of products, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy needs and desires" (Solomon, Bamossy et al. 2006, p6). Different researcher investigate different things such as risk taking in product choice (Cox, 1976), innovation (Mittelstaed et al., 1976; price and Venkatraman 1990) and variety seeking (Pessemier and McAlister, 1982) that effect the consumer behavior. Student of universities and colleges who lived in hostels are consumer of certain products which are exist in the market. Certain researches are conduct that investigates the student buying pattern related online purchase (Yingjiao Xu and V. Ann Paulins, 2005). But very few researches are available which investigate the factor that effect on hostel students buying pattern. This research paper fulfill the gap which exist in the literature and investigate the factor the effects on hostel and boarding students buying behavior.

The theory that provides the theoretical support to this research paper is social learning theory. This theory is derived from the work of Albert Bandura (1963-1964). This theory stated that people learn within social context. According to this theory social behavior is learn and adopt by imitating and observing behavior and action of others. Social behavior is influenced by punishment and rewards of these actions. In this theory he proposed four dimensions Attention, Retention, Reproduction and Motivation that influence the consumer behavior.

The objective of this research is to investigate the factor that affects the buying behavior of hostel student. The research first question is what the factor that affect the hostel student buying behavior? And the second research question is up to what extent there factor effects on hostel student buying behavior?

In this study we offer contributions in a literature. First, we investigate the some confirmation to suggestion some factor that may important for hostel students that affect their buying behavior. Our second contribution is to investigate upto what extent these factor effects on buying behavior of hostel students.

The structure of this research paper is as follow in section 2 we describe the literature in detailed. In section 3, we describe the research methodology and the experimental material that was used in our work, whilst in section 4 we describe what are the factor that effects on hostel students buying behavior and describe the degree these factors. Research findings are presented in section 5, with conclusions being drawn in section 6.

2. Literature Review of student buying behavior

A study was published in 1920 by Jhon B. Watson related to behavior known as “little Albert” (Watson and Rayner 1920). In this study he proved that behavior can be learned by external events and that was discredited the psychodynamic approach which was main at the time. The researcher investigate the different view about the behavior such as Ivan Pavlov (1849-1936) who investigate the classic conditioning and Burrhus skinner (1904-1990) who develop operant conditioning.

In 1993 R.F Lauterborn proposed the 4 Cs related to marketing which is mainly focus for making the strategies related to consumers. The 4 Cs model is more consumer oriented model and focus on niche market. Consumer is a very critical part of 4 Cs. “A consumer is a person or group of people who are the final users of products and or services generated within a social system”. “A consumer may be a person or group, such as a household. Consumer behavior, as any other behavior, is goal-oriented” (Baumgartner & Pieters, 2008). When people decide which products and brands to buy and in which quantity, what to eat for breakfast, what kind of soda to drink, whether to take the bus or drive to work, they do so on account of different goals they are attempting to pursue. The concept related to goal oriented and motivation have been discussed in all areas of consumer behavior including advertising (Wedel & Pieters, 2007), consumer decision making (Fishbach & Dhar, 2005, 2008; Bettman, Luce, & Payne, 1998; Shafir, 2007; Higgins, 2002), product preferences (Luce, Bettman, & Payne 2008), and brand loyalty (Wood, Tam, & Ji, 2009). As Baumgartner and Pieters (2008) stated, “to propose that consumer behavior is goal-directed seems like arguing that water is wet”

Some studies investigate and link the demographic of students and their socio economic background to their buying behavior. In 1995 Xiao found that male students are favourable attitude toward credit cards than female students but they are not differ in paying interest minimum payments (Hayhoe et al., 2000). Students from minority ethnic groups have been found to be more likely to have revolving credit card debt than the general student population (Lyons, 2004; Grable and Joo, 2006; Munro and Hirt, 1998). The students who have high income background they are more knowledgeable related to credit cards but they also carry high debt (Lea & Davies, 1995), and the students who have low income background are more likely to choose minimum payment scheme to pay their debt (Van Venrooij & Lewis, 1995).

Compared with previous studies, the present study has two features. First, we consider the research questions in the context of lifespan transition of university students. Second, we use both quantitative and qualitative methods to explore the research questions.

On the basis of literature we identify following factors which may impact on consumer/students buying behavior.

2.1 Basic needs and consumer behavior

In 1960 (Walter A. Woods) define the two process related to buying decision of product first is the process of motivation (someone needs of foods) and other is the process of discrimination (need is satisfied by particular foods). But what a group of people eat at the particular time is not comes under the motivational factors because these are the products fulfill the basic needs of customers. So on the basis of literature we hypothesis that

H1: *Basic needs of students effects on students buying behavior.*

2.2 Former experience and consumer behavior

Previous consumer experience would be seen as the major predictor of consumer buying behavior. Many researchers describe the relationship between previous experience and consumer buying behavior of consumers such as Udell (1966), Newman and Staelin (1972), and Shaw (1973) they investigate the repurchase of particular product and previous experience and describe the positive relationship between them. So on the basis of literature we hypothesis the

H2: *Former experience has positive effect on consumer buying behavior.*

2.3 Recommended by friends & friends and consumer behavior

The recommendations from the friends and family having great influence on consumer buying behavior. And there recommendations are seriously considered for the buying decision of products. Different researchers usually studied the word of mouth communication that effects on consumers/students behavior (Swartz and Stephens 1983; Kuehl and Ford 1977; Feldman and Spencer 1965; Stewart, Hickson, Ratneshwar, Pechmann, and Altemeier 1985). Brown and Reingen (1987) observed two source of information first is weak tie relationship which have great experience (celebrity) and second strong tie source which have personal relationship with consumers (friends & family). So on the basis of literature we hypothesis

H3: friend and family have effects on consumers/students buying behavior.

2.4 Recommended by celebrities and consumer behavior

The recommendations from the celebrities having great influence on consumer buying behavior. And there recommendations are seriously considered for the buying decision of products. Different researchers usually studied the word of mouth communication that effects on consumers/students behavior (Swartz and Stephens 1983; Kuehl and Ford 1977; Feldman and Spencer 1965; Stewart, Hickson, Ratneshwar, Pechmann, and Altemeier 1985). Brown and Reingen (1987) observed two source of information first is weak tie relationship which have great experience (celebrity) and second strong tie source which have personal relationship with consumers (friends & family). So on the basis of literature we hypothesis

H4: Celebrities have effects on consumers/students buying behavior.

2.5 Products design and consumer behavior

In 1988 (Bruce and Whitehead) was conduct art survey related to product performance in which he stated that 60 percent respondents support the new product and only 17 percent considered price as important. So product design has a great influence on consumer choice. When given the choice between two products, equal in price and function, target consumers buy the one they consider to be more attractive (Nussbaum 1988; Kotler and Rath 1984). So on the basis of literature we hypothesis that

H5: product design has an effect on consumer/students buying behavior.

2.6 Product quality and consumer buying behavior

The Quality can be defined as superiority or excellence. The quality of product on high or low basis and it is depending on excellence or superiority. The consumer perception related to quality is considered as key determinant for buying behavior and product choice (Doyle 1984; Jacoby and Olson 1985; Schlechter 1984; Sawyer and Dickson 1984; Bishop 1984). So on the basis of literature we develop a hypothesis

H6: the product quality will effect on the consumer/students buying behavior.

2.7 Product price and consumer buying behavior

The price of product is most important factor and it is very critically linked with product buying decision. In 1973 (Williams, French and Chance) investigate that if customer does not have enough product knowledge than price used to purchase decision. So on the basis of literature we develop a hypothesis

H7: Product price will effect on the buying behavior of consumer/students.

2.8 Brand and consumer buying behavior

Today in global environment consumer have the availability and awareness about the product brand and product brand heavily influence the purchasing behavior of customers/students. Many researcher have also investigated when information is presented in suitable manner (brand) it is helps both consumers information gaining and comprehension (Betman and Kakkar, 1977; Russo et al., 1986). So on the basis of literature we develop a hypothesis

H8: Brand will effect on the buying behavior of consumer/students.

2.9 Discount on price and consumer buying behavior

Mostly organizations used the discount on price as promotional tools. These types of promotional tools often produce a high consumers response than in regular changes in the price of products Rao and Sabavala (1980) and empirical documented by Guadagni and Little (1983). The discount in the price of products will increase the sales volume of the products. So on the basis of literature we develop a hypothesis

H9: Discount on price will effect on the buying behavior of consumer/students

2.10. Theoretical Framework

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Source of data:

We used the survey approach to collect our primary data. The data has been collected from the hostel students of the various universities of Islamabad.

3.2 Population and sample size:

The data has been collected from the twin cities, since Islamabad is the capital of Pakistan and people from all over the country and all the segments of the society are settled here and also belong to various income groups, therefore we can say that our sample size is the representative of all the population. We distribute the 650 questionnaire and we received the fill questionnaire are 625 & our response rate is 96 percent.

3.3 Questionnaire:

The questionnaire used in our research has been obtained from the article “factor influencing consumer behavior” by Stavkova et al, 2008, which discusses the factors influencing the consumer behavior toward the purchase decision such as I buy because it is a necessity of need.

3.4 Analysis strategy:

The questionnaire has been constructed with a five point likert scale ranging from “1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree” suggested by sounder, lewis and thounhill (2003). The data has been analyzed using statistical software SPSS. In this analysis include descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage to represent the main characteristics of the sample. For the data analysis we used the descriptive statistics such as maximum and minimum. We analyze the each question on the basis of agreement and disagreement values.

4. Data Analysis

The questionnaire has been constructed with a five point likert scale ranging from “1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree” suggested by sounder, lewis and thounhill (2003). The data has been analyzed using statistical software SPSS. In this analysis include descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage to represent the main characteristics of the sample. For the data analysis we used the statistics such as regression and correlation.

Table1: Correlation

Correlations among study variables

	Mean	SD	TIM	ACR	ACS	COURTSY	CONSST	RES	COMPLT	OVRAI
TIM	3.28	1.21	(.85)							
ACR	3.23	1.10	.972**	(.84)						
ACS	2.88	1.06	.565**	.662**	(.86)					
COURTSY	3.11	1.3	.567**	.669**	.632**	(.89),				
CONSST	3.17	1.11	.641**	.725**	.613**	.679**	(.82)			
RES	2.98	1.2	.456**	.568**	.955**	.671**	.661**	(.92)		
COMPLT	2.99	1.17	.502**	.621**	.676**	.672**	.656**	.693**	(.86)	
OVERALL	3.11	1.03	.653**	.756**	.685**	.649**	.653**	.654**	.677**	(.76),

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In table one I calculate the mean, standard deviation and correlation of all variables which are used in hypothesis test. And I show the standard deviation, mean, reliability and correlation of each variable in table 1. To test the reliability of variables I used the Cronbach alpha technique. The values of Cronbach alpha for all the variables time response (.85), timeliness (.85), accuracy (.84), courtesy (.89), consistency (.82), responsive (.92) accessibility (.86), completeness (.86) and overall service quality (.76), I was studied significant at 0.70 level and this level was recommended by (Nunnally, 1978) and this level was also recommended by (Ndubisi, 2006). When I analyze the table 1 , than I see the correlation among overall service quality and time, overall service quality and accuracy, overall service quality and accessibility, overall service quality and courtesy, overall service quality and consistency, overall service quality and responsive, overall service quality and completeness are positive correlate at 0.01 level. In my analysis the value of multi-collinearity within all the independent variables are less than 0.80, so there is no multi-collinearity exists between the independent variables. I found the support of Goldsmith et al., (1999) study related to the multi-collinearity.

Table 2: Regression table

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients	
1	(Constant)	.136	.000		.
	TIM	.153	.000	.180	.000
	ACR	.551	.000	.589	.000
	ACS	.418	.000	.430	.000
	COURTSY	.041	.000	.051	.000
	CONSST	.387	.000	.415	.000
	RES	.051	.000	.221	.000
	COMPLT	.429	.000	.485	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OVRALL

Table 2 describes the regression analysis among time response, timeliness, accuracy; courtesy, consistency, responsive, completeness and accessibility are the independent variable & overall service quality as a dependent variable. The end result of regression table shows that the connection among time and service quality is positive and significant ($\beta=0.180$, $\rho<0.05$). The beta value of job security describe that if one unit increases in job security then job satisfaction will increased by 18 percent. The value is significant because it is lower than 0.05 that's why (H1 time response is positively affects service quality And H2 timeliness is positively affects service quality) are accepted. This study confirms the finding of (Arnold and Feld- man, 1982; Oldham, Julik, Ambrose, Stepina and Brand, 1986).

Relationship between accuracy and service quality is significant ($\beta=0.58$, $\rho<0.05$) it describe that if one unit increase in accuracy then service quality will be increased by 58 percent; (H3, accuracy positively affects service quality) is accepted. This study confirms the finding of (Morey, 1982; Pazer , 1995; Laudon, 1986).

Relationship between courtesy and service quality is significant ($\beta=0.43$, $\rho<0.05$) it describe that if one unit increase in courtesy then service quality will be increased by 43 percent; (H4, courtesy positively affects service quality) is accepted. This study confirms the finding of (Parasuraman et al.'s 1988).

Relationship between consistency and service quality is significant ($\beta=0.051$, $\rho<0.05$) it describe that if one unit increase in consistency then service quality will be increased by 5 percent; (H5, consistency positively affects service quality) is accepted. This study confirms the finding of (Booms and Bitner 1981).

Relationship between responsiveness and service quality is significant ($\beta=0.42$, $\rho<0.05$) it describe that if one unit increase in responsiveness then service quality will be increased by 42 percent; (H6, responsiveness positively affects service quality) is accepted. This study confirms the finding of (Morey, 1982; Pazer , 1995; Laudon, 1986).

Relationship between accessibility and service quality is significant ($\beta=0.22$, $\rho<0.05$) it describe that if one unit increase in accessibility then service quality will be increased by 22 percent; (H7, accessibility positively affects service quality) is accepted. This study confirms the finding of (Litvack and Bodart, 1993; Gilson et al., 1994).

Similarly completeness and service quality is significant ($\beta=0.48$, $\rho<0.05$) it describe that one unit increase in completeness than service quality will be increased by 48 percent. These findings support (H8, which was proposed that completeness has positive effect on service quality).This study confirms the findings of (Michael Portillo,1988).

Discussion and conclusion:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the factor that effect of buying behavior of boarding students such as need, experience, friends and family recommendations, brand, price, product design, discount and workplace.The results show that these factors are significantly related to buying behavior of boarding students.

The results of this study show that the consumer buying behavior is influenced by their need, product quality design brand name and the image of the product as developed by the word of mouth. Hawkins & Coney (1998) noted that consumer buy the products because of their need and that they acquire it for their personal use. The results also highlights that the consumer buying behavior is positively correlated with the product quality and brand and is not affected by discounts offered. Which is not consistent with the findings of Vionea and Filips (2011) who noted that

product buying is also greatly influenced by necessities of life and because of recent economic crisis across the globe the customers preferences are reshaping and that they are willing to sacrifice the product quality and brand name as well in order to find a cheaper product. But this finding is in line with the study of Duhanetal (1997) who also noted that word of mouth is an important factor in buying behavior of consumers and that it plays a positive role in consumer buying patterns. Also Hoyer and Nacinnis (2009) that because of limited knowledge buying seek the help of their family and friends to make a purchase decision. These findings also support the work of Howard and Sheth that consumer acts in a rational way during the buying process as the results show that price and quality greatly influence the consumer behavior. The past experience also positively influence the consumer decision making in buying process and strong evidence is being found in this study, these findings also support the work of Perugini et al. (1999), Norman and Conner (1996).The results also indicate that consumer buying decision is greatly influence because of the service quality because in case of telecomm. Products the service quality and network coverage are the most important factors are vital for the success of the service as noted by Khan (2010). Also in the telecomm sectors the consumer buying behavior is influenced by product quality and that people prefer to buy the same product as of their family and friends as highlighted in this study and noted by (Kapaanda 2012). The conclusion of this study is that the entire factors which are proposed in the literature and theoretical background are effect on the buying behavior of boarding students.

5.1. Significance of the research

To the best of our knowledge we could not find any key research in discussing the user perceptionin the case of boarding students. So this paper is a contribution in this regard. Secondly this paper has discussed one of major issues faced by the Pakistani national i.e the buying behavior of boarding students thus; describing the nature of the services as well, consumer's perception and the overall performance.

5.2. Managerial implication

The marketing manager of corporation can take a feedback from this research to serve the customers in a satisfactory and better manner. The company can sort out the perception and expectations of the customers as well its weaknesses thus to make improvements and developments to have more satisfied customers. This research can also taken as feedback for improvement of marketing efforts by corporations of the country cause almost same nature of the problems are being faced by their customers in other parts of the country.

5.3. Strength and weaknesses

- This paper has focused a leading issue affecting the boarding students in Pakistan.
- This is prime research in Pakistan in case of buying behavior of boarding students.
- The weakness of this research is that it has focused the population of some selective areas of Islamabad/Rawalpindi so it is weaker in regard of generalizability.

5.4. Sample size affect/limitation

The result and findings may vary and even can shift if the population and sample size is increased thus; focusing more areas served by the Islamabad. The results of the data is also vary when their respondents change

5.5. Future direction

- Future Research can be conducted at national level on the boarding students as a whole.
- The sample size should be increased to increase the generalizability of the research.
- Further research can also discuss other aspects of customers expectation and satisfaction

References

- [1] Baumgartner, H., &Pieters, R. (2008). Goal-directed consumer behavior: Motivation, volition, and affect. *In C. P. Haugtvedt, P. M. Herr, & F. R. Kardes (Eds.), Handbook of consumer psychology* 367–392.s
- [2] Bettman, J. R., Luce, M. F., & Payne, J. W. (1998). Constructive consumer choice processes. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 25(3), 187–217.
- [3] Bettman, J. R., Luce, M. F., & Payne, J. W. (2008). Preference construction and preference stability: Putting the pillow to rest. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 18(3), 170–174.
- [4] Bettman, J.R., Kakkar, P., 1977. Effects of information presentation format on consumer information acquisition strategies. *Journal of Consumer Research* 3, 233–240.

- [5] Brown, Jacqueline Johnson and Peter H. Reingen. 1987. "Social Ties and Word-of-Mouth Referral Behavior." *Journal of Consumer Research* 14 (December): 350-362.
- [6] Bruce, Margaret and Maureen Whitehead (1988), "Putting Design into the Picture: The Role of Product Design in Consumer Purchase Behavior," *Journal of the Market Research Society*, 30 (2), 147-62.
- [7] Davies, E. & Stephen E.G.L. (1995) Student attitudes to student debt. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 16, 663–679.
- [8] Feldman, Sidney P. and Merlin C. Spencer. 1965. "The Effect of Personal Influence in the Selection of Consumer Services." In *Marketing and Economic Development*. Ed. Peter Bennett. Chicago: American Marketing Association, 440-452.
- [9] Fishbach, A., & Dhar, R. (2005). Goals as excuses or guides: The liberating effect of perceived goal progress on choice. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 32(3), 370–377.
- [10] Fishbach, A., & Dhar, R. (2008). Dynamics of goal based choice. In C. P. Haugtvedt, P. M. Herr, & F. R. Kardes (Eds.), *Handbook of consumer psychology* (611–637). New York: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [11] Grable, J.E. & Joo, S.-H. (2006) Student racial differences in credit card debt and financial behaviors and stress. *Student College Journal* (40) 400–408
- [12] Guadagni, Peter and John D. C. Little (1983), "A Logit Model of Brand Choice Calibrated on Scanner Data," *Marketing Science*, 2 (Summer), 203-38.
- [13] Hayhoe, C.R., Leach, L.J., Turner, P.R., Bruin, M.J. & Lawrence, F.C. (2000) Differences in spending habits and credit use of college students. *The Journal of Consumer Affairs* (34) 113–133.
- [14] Higgins, E. T. (2002). How self-regulation creates distinct values: The case of promotion and prevention decision making. *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 12(3), 177-191.
- [15] Kotler and G. A. Rath (1984), "Design-A Powerful but Neglected Strategic Tool," *Journal of Business Strategy*, 5 (Fall), 16-21.
- [16] Kuehl, Philip G. and Gary T. Ford. 1977. "The Promotion of Medical and Legal Services: An Experimental Study." In *Contemporary Marketing Thought (AMA Educators' Proceedings)*. Eds. A. G. Greenberg and D. N. Bellenger. Chicago: American Marketing Association, 39-44.
- [17] Lewis, A. & van Venrooij M. (1995) A note on the perceptions of loan duration and repayment. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 16, 161– 168.
- [18] Lyons, A.C. (2004) A profile of financially at-risk college students. *The Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 38, 56–80.
- [19] Munro, J. & Hirt, J.B. (1998) Credit cards and college students: who pays, who benefits? *Journal of College Student Development*, 39, 51–57.
- [20] Newman and Staelin (1972), "Pre purchase Information Seeking for New Cars and Major Household Appliances," *Journal of Marketing Research*, 9 (August), 249-57.
- [21] Nussbaum, Bruce (1988), "Smart Design," *Business Week*, (April 11), 102-17.
- [22] Rao, Vithala R. and Darius J. Sabavala (1980), "Allocation of Marketing Resources: The Role of Price Promotions," in *Proceedings of the Second Market Measurement Conference*, Robert Leone, ed. Providence, RI: TIMS College of Marketing.
- [23] Russo, J.E., Staelin, R., Nolan, C.A., Russell, G.J., Metcalf, B.L., 1986. Nutrition information in the supermarket. *Journal of Consumer Research* 13(June), 48–70.
- [24] Shafir, E. (2007). Decisions constructed locally: Some fundamental principles of the psychology of decision making. In A. W. Kruglanski, & E. T. Higgins (Eds.), *Social psychology: Handbook of basic principles* (334–352).
- [25] Shaw, J. J. (1973), "The Use of Types of Information Sources by Pre purchase and Post purchase Home Buying Consumers," unpublished DBA thesis, University of Oklahoma.
- [26] SKINNER, B. F., 1938. The behavior of organisms. An Experimental Analysis. In: *New York: Appleton-Century*

- [27] Stewart, David W., Gerald B. Hickson, Srinivasan Ratneshwar, Corneha Pechmann, and William Altemeier. 1985. "Information Search and Decision Strategies Among Health Care Consumers." *Advances in Consumer Research* (12)252-257.
- [28] Swartz, Teresa A. and Nancy Stephens. 1983. "Marketing Professional Services: The Case of the Physician." In Proceedings of the 1983 Convention of the American Academy of Advertising. Ed. Donald Jugenheimer. Lawrence, KS: *American Academy of Advertising*, 78-82.
- [29] Tam, L., Wood, W., & Ji, M. F. (2009). Brand loyalty is not habitual. In D. J. MacInnis, C. W. Park, & J. R. Priester (Eds.), *Handbook of brand relationships*, 43–62.
- [30] Udell, J. G. (1966), "Prepurchase Behavior of Buyers of Small Electrical Appliances," *Journal of Marketing*, 30 (October), 50-2.
- [31] WATSON, J., et al., 1920. Conditioned Emotional Reactions. *Journal of Experimental Psychology* 3, (1) 1-14.
- [32] Xiao, J.J., Noring, F.E. & Anderson, J.G. (1995) College students' attitudes towards credit cards. *Journal of Consumer Studies and Home Economics*, (19)155–174.